

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Regional premiums in nonferrous metals markets

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Email: christopher.gilbert@jhu.edu**Abstract**

Peculiarities of the LME contract structure give the impression that exchange spot prices measure transaction prices paid by consumers and received by producers. This impression can be misleading. Transaction prices also include a regional premium that can account for a substantial component of the full price. In well-supplied markets, premiums measure the cost of intermediating exchange warehouses and consumers. In periods of tight demand they reflect the urgency of consumer requirements. I use a Markov-switching model to analyze the regional and temporal variation in aluminum and zinc premiums.

KEYWORDS

aluminum, exchange warehouses, Markov switching, metals, premiums, zinc

1 | INTRODUCTION

The major nonferrous metals are traded on the London Metal Exchange (LME) with copper also traded on the Chicago Mercantile Exchange (CME) NYMEX market. The LME differs in important respects from the standard futures model both in terms of contract structure (daily rather than monthly or other periodic) contracts and its global (not regional) warehouse network. The consequence is that LME Settlement prices on its daily prompt contracts can sustain a worldwide cash price interpretation. However, this price is the cash price of a warehouse warrant, not of the metal itself. Regional premiums drive a wedge between the prices paid by metal consumers and the exchange price.

In aluminum, which is the most valuable of the LME metals in terms of exchange volume, the US regional premium is known as the Midwest Premium (MWP), and the full price, which is the LME price plus the premium, is the Midwest Transaction Price (MWTP). At its maximum, the premium amounted to more than 20% of the MWTP. High premiums have also occurred in the zinc market. Reference to LME prices in these situations substantially understates the prices paid by consumers and received by producers. By contrast, in copper, where the LME competes with NYMEX, premiums have been low and stable.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses the peculiar features of LME contracts and their implications for prices. Section 3 looks at pricing practice in nonferrous metals and the mechanics of premium determination. It provides a descriptive analysis of premium variation over time and across regions (United States, Europe, and Asia) and discusses the factors that determine premiums. In well-supplied markets, premiums are competed down to the cost of intermediating exchange warehouses and consumers. These costs may be affected by the geographical location of warehouse stocks and the degree of competition in the warehouse services industry. However, when demand is tight, premiums reflect the urgency of consumer requirements and can spike in an analogous manner to the futures backwardation.

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In Section 4, I relate this discussion to the Midwest and Rotterdam aluminum and zinc premiums and also the Japanese aluminum premium. Aluminum saw elevated premiums that resulted from congestion in warehouse load-outs with load-out queues of over 2 years. Load-out queues also afflicted the zinc market over the same period but zinc also experienced a major premium spike (around 10% of the full price) during the tight demand period of 2006–07. I show that premium behavior can be modeled by a Markovian regime-switching model with two states—a base state corresponding to a well-supplied market in which premiums are competed down to the cost of obtaining metal from an exchange warehouse and a tight demand state in which premiums can spike to very high levels. Section 5 draws conclusions.

2 | FUTURES EXCHANGES

Futures contracts on the major nonferrous metals are traded on the LME and the Shanghai Futures Exchange (SHFE). Copper futures are traded additionally on the CME NYMEX futures market. The LME is the most liquid nonferrous futures market outside China. LME prices set the benchmark for commerce in nonferrous metals in aluminum, lead, nickel, tin, and zinc throughout the entire world excluding mainland China. In copper, LME and NYMEX prices, which are closely arbitrated, provide competing benchmarks.

Commodity futures markets typically aim to concentrate liquidity on a small number of grades and delivery locations. Futures prices are tied to cash prices by the delivery mechanism. Contracts give the short party the option of determining the grade delivered and the location of delivery. This option provides an incentive to deliver the cheapest-to-deliver grade permitted by the contract in the cheapest-to-deliver of the stipulated delivery locations.¹ Futures prices can therefore be expected to converge on the spot price of that grade in that location at the contract maturity date since otherwise riskless profits could be made by buying the future and selling cash or vice versa (Hull, 2017, p. 44). Prices of other grades and in other locations will be higher by an amount sufficient to deter holders from arbitrating the differences.

Futures markets provide a benchmark for cash prices, but the latter will generally exceed the futures price of the front contract. Discussing US grains markets, Hieronymus (1971, pp. 152–153) recorded, “... even the most casual student is aware that the cash prices of storable commodities ... are nearly always higher than the futures during delivery months.” This cash premium will be higher the more distant (in terms of transport costs) is the cash market in question from the cheapest-to-deliver location under the futures contract. Despite this, cash premiums are generally small and relatively constant within the region that the futures market serves. In many markets, nonpar grades are deliverable subject to premiums or discounts set by the exchange and the same can apply to delivery locations—see Garbade and Silber (1983), Gay and Manaster (1984), and Edwards and Ma (1992, Sec. 15.2.2), all of which discuss US grains markets. As a consequence, it is acceptable to regard front futures prices as benchmarking cash prices in the region covered by the exchange. For example, the front CME (NYMEX) West Texas Intermediate (WTI) crude oil price provides a reliable benchmark throughout the United States and Canada² but only an approximate benchmark in Europe and Asia.

This standard account does not apply directly to nonferrous metals. The LME differs from the standard US exchange model in important respects. Whereas standard futures markets specify delivery locations in a single location or a relatively small range of locations in which cash prices may be expected to differ little, the LME allows delivery to warehouses throughout the United States, Western Europe, and Asia (excluding mainland China).³ Furthermore, the LME trades a large number of contracts for each metal such that one contract becomes “prompt” (i.e., expires) on each trading day—see Edwards and Ma (1992, Sec. 15.5.2). The Settlement Price of the prompt contract thereby becomes interpretable as the cash price of the metal in question on that day throughout North America, Western Europe, and Asia. Nevertheless, metal availability and demand conditions will both vary across locations and transactions prices in

¹See Hull (2017, pp. 154–155) on the cheapest-to-deliver bond.

²At least to the east of the Rocky Mountains. See <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/GAOREPORTS-GAO-07-315/html/GAOREPORTS-GAO-07-315.htm>.

³According to the LME website, “There are 500 LME-approved warehouses in 34 separate locations across the USA, Europe and Asia.” (Not all warehouses are registered for all metals traded on the LME). <https://www.lme.com/en-GB/Trading/Warehousing/Approved-warehouses>. The government of the PRC has not allowed the LME to open warehouses in mainland China which remains exclusively served by the SHFE. Foreign exchange and other restrictions limit direct access to the LME from China.

commercial contracts inevitably reflect these differences. These transactions prices differ from LME cash prices by regional differentials.

Copper is an intermediate case since it is traded both on NYMEX, which trades standard monthly contracts, as well as on the LME. The NYMEX copper warehouses are all in the United States.⁴ Expiring NYMEX contracts converge on US cash prices and the close arbitrage between the NYMEX and LME markets ensures that both front NYMEX and LME Settlement prices are close to US transaction prices. For the remaining major LME metals (aluminum, lead, nickel, tin, and zinc), interpretation of LME Settlement prices on prompt contracts as cash prices is only approximately valid and can be misleading. For these metals, it is preferable to refer to published regional transactions prices published by price reporting agencies.

As emphasized in Goldman Sachs (2013), LME futures prices define the price a purchaser will pay for a warehouse warrant, not for the metal itself. Ownership of the warrant entitles the bearer to take delivery of the metal specified in the warrant. Goldman Sachs (2013, p. 1) states, “The LME price is not the price that consumers pay for physical aluminium, but rather the value of a warrant for delivery to the cheapest warehouse anywhere in the world.” Actual transactions prices differ from the LME price by premiums which reflect the costs of intermediating consumers and exchanges. Consumers pay the premiums to avoid the costs and inconvenience of taking delivery from an exchange warehouse or because their requirements are urgent. Because both demand conditions and the costs of accessing exchange warehouses can differ across regions, premiums will be regional and transaction prices for nonferrous metals will also have a regional dimension even though they are all based on the same exchange price. Section 3 explores the relation between exchange and transaction prices in greater detail.

3 | PREMIUMS AND TRANSACTIONS PRICES

It is very unusual for metal fabricators or semifabricators to purchase metal by holding a long position in a futures contract to expiry and then taking delivery of the metal. If purchasing from an exchange, the short party to an expiring futures contract has the option to choose which warrant to deliver against an expiring contract. For example, the LME aluminum contract allows delivery of P1020A aluminum in three different “shapes”—ingots, *t*-bars, and sows while the nickel contract allows delivery of cathodes (full plate or cut), pellets, and briquettes.⁵ The seller can also choose the “brand” (i.e., the producer). Finally, the seller can also choose the location of the warehouse from which delivery will take place. Only by chance will the seller’s choice of shape and warehouse be the most convenient for the purchaser. Brokers can arrange to swap the warrant for one better suited to the purchaser’s requirements but this will entail a fee.

In general consumers purchase metal either directly from a producer or from a merchant. In this way, they can obtain metal of their required specification delivered directly to their premises—see Adams (2019, pp. 104–108) for discussion. It is open to producers and consumers to negotiate contracts on any terms they wish provided this is within the law. Contracts may either be spot or specify forward sales. Nevertheless, certain contracting forms have become standard across the entire world nonferrous industry. Many, perhaps the majority, of metal consumers will make forward contracts covering deliveries over a number of months. Often these will be contracts for an entire calendar year.

Outside China, *forward contracts* for the purchase of the major metals traded on the LME will typically have three components (see United States Senate, 2014, pp. 171–172):

- (i) the exchange price;
- (ii) the relevant regional premium; and
- (iii) a contract-specific premium.

Regional premiums measure the marginal cost of intermediating exchanges and consumers. Consumers avoid these costs by purchasing directly from a producer. Intermediation costs reflect costs imposed as the consequence of the seller’s grade and location option but also any additional transaction costs arising out of exchange purchase. These costs will reflect the efficiency and competitive structure of the exchange warehouse market.

⁴<https://www.cmegroup.com/trading/metals/base/base-metals-warehousing.html>.

⁵<https://www.lme.com/Metals/Non-ferrous/Aluminium/Physical>, <https://www.lme.com/en-GB/Metals/Non-ferrous/Nickel/Physical>.

The exchange price component of a forward transaction price will generally specify the calendar month average of LME (spot) Settlement prices over the month in which delivery takes place (In some cases, the prior month average may be specified). In the US copper market, the average price of the NYMEX front contract is often used in place of the LME price. These are floating prices, that is, they are not known at the time of contracting, and so generate an incentive to hedge.

The regional premium components of nonferrous metals transactions prices are established price reporting agencies.⁶ Platts, now part of S&P, is the dominant reporting agency in the United States. *Metal Bulletin*, now Fastmarkets, competes with Platts and has a strong position in Europe. In the US, premiums are generally known as the MWP and in Europe as the Rotterdam Premium but these premiums have general reference throughout North America and Western Europe, respectively. The regional premium in a forward purchase contract may either be fixed at the time of contracting or may be on the same floating basis as the LME component. Reference to floating premiums has become more prevalent over the past decade during which premium volatility has tended to increase. Floating contracts sometimes allow the option of fixing one or both price components at an intermediate date between contracting and delivery. The sum of the LME or NYMEX spot price and the regional premium is known as the all-in or full price. Platts has formalized the full price concept in the US aluminum market as the MWTP and this has become the most widely used contracting basis in that market.

The third component on the contract price is contract-specific and is negotiated between the buyer and the seller. This will reflect product specifications, which may differ from those specified in LME and NYMEX contracts, delivery location, the quantity transacted, payment terms, and credit status. This price component is generally small for significant purchases of products of standard specification and shows relatively little variation over time.

Consumers cannot always accurately predict their metal requirements months ahead. Consequently, they will typically contract forward for less than their entire expected requirements to avoid over-ordering in the event of a downturn in demand. They then make up the remainder of their requirements through spot purchases, either from a producer or from a merchant. The same three price components will be reflected in *spot contracts with producers* although these contracts will often specify the MWTP, or the LME (or NYMEX) price and the MWP, on the date of contracting rather than as a monthly average. The regional and contract-specific premiums may not always be separately distinguished in spot sales contacts.

The situation is different in *spot purchases from the merchant market* which are negotiated on a contract-by-contract basis. Merchants will seek to obtain prices in relation to metal availability and the urgency of consumer requirements. Merchant markets become particularly important when the supply–demand balance is tight and producers are unable or unwilling to deliver additional tonnages within a short time-frame. The price reporting agencies survey merchants and their reported premiums. Transaction prices are calculated as truncated averages of spot transactions prices for standard grades over the reporting period and premiums are inferred as the difference between the quoted transaction price and the exchange price over the same period.⁷ It is difficult to obtain information on the volume and size of merchant transactions.

In summary, regional premiums are determined on the residual merchant market and then form part of the pricing basis in the producer market. Pricing follows the same format in Europe and Asia. In Europe, the Rotterdam Premium plays the same role as the MWP in the US. Asia is more heterogeneous with different premiums quoted for Japan, Korea, and Singapore.

3.1 | Premium variation

I start by examining temporal variation in the MWP for the main LME nonferrous metals. Figure 1 charts monthly averages for the aluminum, copper, nickel, and zinc premiums over the period September 2003–June 2019 normalized onto a September 2003 = 100 basis. (See the appendix for premium definitions and sources). The most prominent features are the two large spikes in the nickel premium over the period 2007–11.

Figure 2 graphs the same premiums as a share of the MWTP and includes the lead premium, which has only been reported by Platts from May 2014. The nickel premium spikes are less pronounced as a share of the full price since they

⁶Duffie et al. (2017) have shown that, except when markets are already efficient, the existence of benchmark prices raises welfare in over-the-counter (OTC) financial markets by increasing the information available to purchasers, reducing wasteful search costs and improving matching efficiency. Adams (2019, pp. 94–96) discusses the role of price reporting agencies in the metals industries.

⁷This is current practice. It appears that historically, the reporting agencies surveyed spot premiums and inferred the full (transaction) price.

FIGURE 1 Midwest Premiums—aluminum, copper, nickel, and zinc (January 2003 = 100)

FIGURE 2 Midwest Premiums—share of the full price, aluminum, copper, lead, nickel, and zinc

occurred at the same times as spikes in the nickel exchange price. Instead, the graph is dominated by the two periods of elevated aluminum premiums in 2013–14 and 2018–19. In both cases, the premium rose to around 20% of the full price. The other prominent feature of Figure 2 is the persistently low and stable copper premium.

Table 1 gives descriptive statistics, both over the entire 19.5-year period January 2000–June 2019 and over 4-year subperiods. The statistics confirm that copper consistently saw the lowest and least volatile premiums and that, leaving lead aside where only a short premium history is available, aluminum had generally the highest and often the most volatile premiums. The nickel premium mixes periods of high and volatile premiums with tranquil low premium periods.

Because premiums are regional, the extent to which they comove will depend on the extent to which the driving factors are common as distinct from regionally specific. This balance may be different from different metals and may vary over time for the same metal. Figure 3 charts the Midwest, Rotterdam, and Japanese premiums for aluminum, the metal for which comovement is most pronounced. The major spike in premiums in 2014 and the first half of 2015 is common across all three regional markets. By contrast, the high 2018–19 premium is specific to the United States and reflects the 10% tariff on aluminum imports into the United States introduced in March 2018. The broken dark line in Figure 3 shows the duty-unpaid premium which moves more closely in line with the Rotterdam and Japanese premiums.

Table 2 reports the interregional premium correlation over the period September 2003 (the date of the first Platts quotes for the Rotterdam aluminum and nickel premiums) to June 2016. For aluminum, I use the duty-unpaid premium. The correlations are highest for aluminum and lowest for copper with nickel and zinc intermediate.⁸ An alternative way of quantifying comovement is to look at the proportion of overall premium variance explained by the

⁸The lead premium time series is insufficiently long to allow inclusion in Tables 2 and 3. Platts does not report an Asian nickel premium and the Platts Singapore zinc premium terminates in April 2017. Price reporting agencies will generally not report prices for which they have insufficient information.

TABLE 1 Descriptive statistics—Midwest Premium share of the US full price

	2003–07 ^a (%)	2008–11 (%)	2012–15 (%)	2016–19 ^b (%)	2003–19 ^c (%)
<i>Aluminum</i>					
Average	5.3	5.6	13.7	12.8	9.1
s.d.	2.1	1.3	4.5	4.4	5.1
<i>Copper</i>					
Average	2.9	1.4	1.8	2.1	2.1
s.d.	1.2	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.9
<i>Lead</i>					
Average				9.0	9.8
s.d.				1.2	1.4
<i>Nickel</i>					
Average	3.8	5.9	2.3	6.6	4.6
s.d.	0.7	2.6	0.7	3.1	2.6
<i>Zinc</i>					
Average	6.0	4.2	9.1	8.3	6.9
s.d.	1.7	1.3	1.1	0.7	2.3

^aSeptember 2003–December 2007.^bJanuary 2016–June 2019.^cSeptember 2003–June 2019.

FIGURE 3 Midwest, Rotterdam, and Japanese aluminum premiums

TABLE 2 Interregional premium correlations, September 2003–June 2016

	Midwest/Rotterdam	Midwest/Asia	Rotterdam/Asia
Aluminum	0.912	0.886	0.968
Copper	0.362	0.159	0.399
Nickel	0.551		
Zinc	0.519	0.437	-0.113

Note: The correlations involving the Asian (Singapore) zinc premium are over the period September 2003–April 2017.

TABLE 3 Proportion of premium variance explained by leading principal component

	Aluminum (%)	Copper (%)	Nickel (%)	Zinc (%)
Midwest, Rotterdam, and Asia	94.6	54.1	–	55.4 ^a
Midwest and Rotterdam	95.6	63.8	77.5	76.0

Note: Sample: September 2003–June 2019.

^aSample ends September 2017.

leading principal component. Table 3 reports these proportions both including and excluding the Asian premiums which have a poor correlation with the other two in the cases of copper and zinc. In aluminum, 95% of premium variation appears common while for the other three metals this proportion drops to between 60% and 75%. There is very little correlation between the principal components of the four metals.

The overall conclusion is that although there is only a modest correlation between premiums for different metals, in each case there is significant premium comovement across regions. This comovement is most pronounced in aluminum where the regional premiums move very closely together, and least pronounced in copper.

3.2 | Premium determination

Premiums are the margins between commercial transaction prices and exchange prices. They are determined by two sets of factors: the intermediation costs of obtaining exchange metal of the desired specification in a convenient location and the tightness of the market for physical metal. I first consider intermediation costs.

In well-supplied markets, the premium will be determined by the value the purchaser puts on avoiding the costs and inconvenience of purchasing from the exchange. Under these conditions, premiums solely reflect intermediation costs. Financial institutions are likely to dominate warrant purchase. These institutions will often rewarehouse and continue to store the metal to profit from the margin between the contango and the cost of storage.

One factor that can affect intermediation costs is the geographical distribution of exchange warehouses, and of stocks across the warehouse system. Hieronymus (1971, p. 341) noted “Proliferation of delivery points results in distortion of price relationships over space. Delivery will be made at the point of lowest value and cash prices at other points are above this by commercial value differences.” The short party in an expiring contract will have an incentive to purchase a low-value warrant for this delivery, or swap a currently-held higher value warrant for the low-value warrant. For some LME metals, in particular aluminum, the shift in the balance of consumption from North America to Asia has implied an increase in the probability that an Asian warrant will be delivered against an expiring contract. A purchaser seeking US delivery will likely have to pay a fee to swap an Asian for a US warrant on the OTC warrant market. This issue does not arise in copper since all the NYMEX warehouses are in the United States.

Intermediation costs can also be affected by competition in the provision of exchange warehouse services. LME warehouses are operated by 27 separate warehousing groups.⁹ This number might appear sufficient to ensure competitive outcomes. Despite this large number, competition can become compromised if stocks become concentrated in a small number of locations. Stock concentration tends to be persistent since the purchaser of an LME warrant is very likely to receive a warrant specifying metal in a warehouse in which stocks are high. Elevated concentration can arise either through the free operation of competitive markets or through an attempt by warehouse operators to obtain a dominant position. A warehouse operator is able to develop a dominant position by paying incentives to attract metal. Rent-sharing arrangements, in which the warehouse operator discounts space rental rates, appear relatively standard but there is little documentation of the extent and size of these incentives. US Senate (2014, pp. 186–195) documents payment of freight and other incentives to attract and retain aluminum in the LME Detroit warehouses.

A high level of stock concentration allows the potential for the warehouse operator to increase the price of warehouse services or the length of time that metal is warehoused and hence for which rental is due. The LME zinc market saw a dramatic increase in the concentration of exchange warehouse stocks in a single warehouse location

⁹Based on the August 2019 figures reported in <https://www.lme.com/en-GB/Market-Data/Reports-and-data/Warehouse-and-stocks-reports/Warehouse-and-queue-data>. Many groups operate legally as a number of different companies in different jurisdictions. NYMEX has eight warehouses across the US.

(New Orleans) peaking at 99% in 2017. In Section 4.3, I examine the impact of this high concentration level on zinc premiums.

Load-out queues trap metal in warehouses potentially raising revenues to warehouse operators. Queues in loading metals out of exchange warehouses have afflicted the LME aluminum and zinc markets over the most recent decade.¹⁰ These queues potentially raise the cost of exchange purchase by creating a delay between metal purchase and the subsequent delivery. The delay results in additional interest and warehouse rental costs and makes exchange purchase unsuited for urgent requirements. The purchasers of warrants that designate metal in queued warehouses find themselves at the back of a load-out queue. The warehouse operator will receive rental income over an extended period thereby enabling payment of incentives to attract further metal. Figure 5 charts the Detroit aluminum load-out queues and the New Orleans zinc load-out queue.¹¹

Futures market theory indicates that the short party of an expiring contract will deliver the least valuable warrant. In the presence of load-out queues, this is likely to be a warrant from a queued warehouse.¹² If there are queues at more than one warehouse location, warrants from the warehouse with the longest queue will be the least valuable so premiums should be expected to rise by the cost of taking delivery from that location. The purchaser of a warrant in a queued location will likely swap that warrant for a more expensive warrant in a location without a queue and take delivery from that location. The consequence is that metal will tend to remain in the queue-ridden locations.

Demand conditions are the second major set of factors that affect premiums. When the market becomes tight producers may find it difficult to schedule additional deliveries in a timely manner resulting in consumers moving to the merchant market. This will allow merchants to raise prices above marginal cost. As these prices are reported to S&P Platts, the MWP will rise leading to a greater margin between the full price and the exchange price.

Premiums therefore behave in a similar manner to the futures backwardation. This is illustrated in Figure 4 for the Midwest zinc premium. The 2006 zinc premium spike was mirrored in the backwardation but the increasing backwardation in 2018–19 left the premium unaffected.¹³ Although premiums are subject to the same types of spikes as spot futures prices, the factors which drive these spikes are only in part common to the physical and futures markets.

One consequence is that premiums generally show a positive correlation with the futures backwardation—see Table 4 where the correlations are all positives except in the case of aluminum. This correlation may suggest that movements in the backwardation can cause movements in the premium but this is a confusion. The extent to which the market is in contango or backwardation affects the costs of storage but not the costs of intermediation between the exchange warehouse and the consumer. The likely reason for the positive correlation is that demand factors that result in high premiums also cause a high backwardation resulting in the premium-backwardation correlation. This is a case of the grass being green when the river is high—it has recently rained so the two phenomena are correlated but neither causes the other.¹⁴

To conclude, so long as producers are able to satisfy consumer requirements in a timely and efficient manner, premiums are competed down to the cost of accessing exchange metal. Premiums may differ in different parts of the world and may vary over time. Specifically, they may reflect inefficiencies and monopolistic actions in the warehouse services market. However, in periods of tight demand in which producers cannot quickly meet consumer requirements in their entirety, premiums will respond to the urgency on the part of consumers. In these circumstances, premiums share characteristics of the futures backwardation—although premiums are not caused by the futures contango or backwardation, they share the same two regime behavior. This motivates the use of a regime-switching model to account for historical premium movements.

¹⁰See Kocieniewski (2013) and Stevens and Zhang (2017).

¹¹The major load-out queues (Detroit, New Orleans, and also Vlissingen in the Netherlands) all disappeared by the end of 2017. However, new queues emerged in 2018 in the LME's Asian warehouses, in particular in Port Klang (Malaysia, mainly aluminum) but also in Johor (Malaysia, aluminum and zinc) and Busan (Korea, aluminum).

¹²Before an LME rule change announced in November 2012 and that took effect in April 2013, queues were not metal-specific. As a consequence, the longest queue could occur in a warehouse with a relatively small stock of the metal in question. The most important instance of this was in zinc where small tonnages were blocked behind a long load-out queue consisting mainly of aluminum. In this circumstance, it is unclear whether warrants from that warehouse would be available for delivery.

¹³The nickel premium and backwardation exhibit the same features: a premium spike in April 2007 and in May and June 2010. The first of these coincided with a heightened backwardation in the futures market which nevertheless remained in contango through the premium spike in the spring of 2010. The sharp backwardation in the early summer of 2014 left the premium market largely unaffected.

¹⁴"The river is high and the stream is strong and the grass is green and tall/And I fain would think that this world of ours is a good world after all." Henry Lawson. <https://www.poetrylibrary.edu.au/poets/lawson-henry/poems/after-all-0002047>.

FIGURE 4 Zinc backwardation and Midwest and Rotterdam zinc premiums

TABLE 4 Premium-backwardation correlations

	Aluminum	Copper	Lead ^a	Nickel	Zinc
Midwest Premium	-0.106	0.605	n.a.	0.073	0.556
Rotterdam Premium	-0.222	0.294	0.336	0.559	0.593

Note: Sample: Monthly averages, September 2003–June 2019.

The 3-month backwardation is adjusted by subtracting the 90-day AA Financial Commercial Paper Interest Rate (RIFSPFAAD90NB). Both the premiums and backwardation are delated by the US Producer Price Index (all items).

^aThe Platts Midwest lead premium is only quoted from May 2013.

4 | ALUMINUM AND ZINC

This section looks specifically at determination of the aluminum and zinc premiums focusing on determination of spikes in the premiums. Copper is uninteresting in this regard since there were no major premium spikes over the period analyzed and lack of a long premium series prevents analysis of lead. The nickel market is more complicated than those for aluminum and zinc making the concept of a nickel market balance less tractable. (The major end-use is in the manufacture of stainless steel in which the nickel content varies according to specification and which is largely produced directly from ferronickel of varying nickel concentration). Second, both the aluminum and zinc premiums have been affected by variables that I can identify as affecting exchange intermediation costs, specifically load-out queues from exchange warehouses and changes in the regional location of warehouse stocks—see Sections 4.2 and 4.3. I am unaware of comparable factors that might have affected nickel intermediation costs—there have been no nickel load-out queues and until recently LME warehouse stocks of nickel have been almost entirely in Europe.

4.1 | Methodology

I use the following premium model for both aluminum and zinc:

$$prem_t = \alpha + \beta z_t + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j x_{jt} + u_t \quad (t = 1, \dots, T), \quad (1)$$

where z is a measure of the regional market balance, the x variables measure exchange intermediation costs, u is an error term distributed as $u_{mt} \sim N(0, \sigma_m^2)$. Equation (1) can be estimated by OLS. I use monthly average data for the premiums and estimate over the sample September 2003 (the first month for which Platts publishes Rotterdam and Japanese premium data for aluminum) to June 2019.

In Section 3, I argued that premiums are responsive to demand conditions in the tight demand regime but not in the well-supplied regime. This view is incorporated by allowing the intercept α and the coefficient β of the market balance

variable to vary across regimes. A simple way to incorporate premium spikes would be the inclusion of a dummy variable to cover such periods. However, this requires that these periods can be dated a priori. The Hamilton (1989, 1990) Markov-switching methodology allows the different regimes to be determined by the data. With two regimes (0 and 1), the procedure estimates probabilities π_{01} and π_{10} of switching from Regime 0 to Regime 1 and from Regime 1 to Regime 0, respectively. Equation (1) becomes

$$prem_t = \sum_{r=0}^1 p_t^r [\alpha^r + \beta^r z_t] + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j x_{jt} + u_t \quad (t = 1, \dots, T), \quad (2)$$

where p_t^r is the probability that premiums are governed by regime r in period t . These probabilities evolve according to the Markovian transition equation

$$\begin{aligned} p_t^0 &= (1 - \pi_{01})p_{t-1}^0 + \pi_{01}p_{t-1}^1, \\ p_t^1 &= \pi_{10}p_{t-1}^0 + (1 - \pi_{10})p_{t-1}^1. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Regime 0 is the well-supplied regime and Regime 1 the tight demand regime so we identify the regimes through the inequality $\alpha_m^1 > \alpha_m^0$. Estimation is by Maximum Likelihood (ML). The estimates allow the investigator to back out the probabilities p_t^0 and p_t^1 that the market was in Regimes 0 and 1, respectively, in each period t .¹⁵

If the two regimes were clearly demarcated and the switch points known ex ante, the Markov-switching model would be equivalent to the interacted dummy variable model in which the probabilities p_t^r are replaced by exogenously given dummy regime indicator variables. In that case, the move from Equation (1) to (2) would be akin to inclusion of a data-based dummy variable in the equations and, as with all dummy-based models, it does not offer an account as to why the intercept differs across regimes. This leaves the Markov-switching model open to the charge of data-mining. Nevertheless, the approach has two important implications. First, if regime switches are correlated with the x regressor variables in Equation (1), the OLS coefficient estimates of Equation (1) will be biased and inconsistent. Second, associated standard errors are likely to be overnarrow by failing to take into account the possibility of a jump in the equation intercept. More generally, the estimated probabilities p_t^r will typically differ from zero and one so that, conditional on past information, the estimation procedure will regard the process as sharing the properties of the two regimes.

I aim to test two hypotheses within this framework. The first hypothesis (A) relates to departures from linearity. Equations (2) and (3) simplify to a standard linear model (3) if the following conditions hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^1 &= \alpha^0, \\ H_A: \beta^1 &= \beta^0, \\ \pi^{10} &= \pi^{01} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The second hypothesis (B) asks whether premium spikes are associated with tight market balance. I identify the premium spike regimes by the normalization $\alpha^1 > \alpha^0$. If these spikes are associated with tight demand, we require the inequality $\beta^1 > \beta^0$. The null hypothesis of no response difference is therefore $H_B: \beta^1 = \beta^0$.

The Hamilton switching specification (1) makes the estimated very sensitive to the precise specification of the market balance variable z . I have followed metals industry practice in modeling market tightness by the quarterly regional market balance (the difference between metal primary consumption and production) deflated by the trend in consumption. These balances were calculated for the USA, Europe (EU28), and (aluminum only) for Asia.¹⁶ The crude balance figures were interpolated on a monthly basis using the standard cubic spline procedure. Finally, the resulting

¹⁵Garcia and Perron (1996) used the Hamilton (1989, 1990) regime-switching model to analyze the evolution of real interest rates. The model has also been widely used in modeling conditional volatilities in financial markets, including the crude oil futures market as in Ma et al. (2017). Equation (2) restricts the γ coefficients to be invariant across regimes. This assumption is testable but allowance of too much flexibility can yield convergence problems. Markov-switching estimates were Markov-switching estimates were obtained using OxMetrics. See (Doornik, 2018).

¹⁶Source for quarterly consumption and production figures: CRU Group Ltd. Figures exclude production and consumption from recycled metal. The aluminum consumption trend is log-linear while that for zinc is a smooth trend in log consumption using STAMP (Koopman et al., 2009). Both trends have a downward level jump in 2008q4. An earlier draft of the paper used changes in regional industrial production indices to measure market tightness. While this performed satisfactorily for the US aluminum market it gives less clear results for zinc premiums and for the European and Japanese aluminum premiums.

FIGURE 5 The Detroit aluminum and New Orleans zinc load-out queues

adjusted monthly series were demeaned, detrended, and deseasonalized using the structural time series analyser, modeler, and predictor procedure (STAMP; Koopman et al., 2009).

The *balance* variable enters into the equations averaged over 3 months and lagged 3 months (6 months in the case of the Rotterdam zinc premium). The lag suggests that imbalances between metal consumption and supplies from smelters need to cumulate over time before affecting premiums. The market balance variable is defined such that positive values indicate an excess of consumption over production.

4.2 | Aluminum premiums

Figure 3 charts the deflated Midwest, Rotterdam, and Japanese premiums. The following features are evident:

- The MWP has tended to rise over time even in real terms and at the same time the differential over the Rotterdam and Japanese premiums has tended to widen.
- All three regional premiums rose following the Global Financial Crisis peaking at the end of 2014 and then collapsed back.
- The duty-paid MWP rose sharply in March 2018 following the imposition of a 10% import tariff into the United States. Imports accounted for 88.2% of US aluminum consumption in 2018 so the incidence of the tariff was almost entirely on US aluminum consumers. The duty-unpaid premium moved in line with the Rotterdam and Japanese premiums. In what follows I analyze the duty-unpaid premium.
- The periods of acute backwardation were all before the Global Financial Crisis with the highest peak at the start of 2007. The futures market moved away from full carry during the high premium period in 2014–15 but backwardations were low compared with earlier in the sample.

The rise in premiums over the 4 years 2010–13 took place in a weak market with the contango near full carry. This suggests that the higher premium was due to increased intermediation costs. The likely cause was the emergence of long load-out queues from the LME exchange warehouse in Detroit, charted in Figure 5. The Detroit queue (length *qdt*) emerged at the end of 2010 in part as the consequence of the sharp decline in aluminum consumption which had led to an accumulation of inventory in the LME's Detroit warehouse location. Changes in LME warehouse regulations that became effective from 2015 (London Metal Exchange, 2013) made it unattractive for warehouse operators to allow queues to build up with the consequence that the Detroit queues shortened and disappeared by mid-2016.¹⁷

¹⁷End-month queue lengths have been published by the LME starting in April 2014. Queue lengths before this date were calculated from the stock of canceled warrants in conjunction with the minimum load-out rate dictated by prevailing LME warehousing rules—see Gilbert (2021b) for details. There was also a load-out queue in the LME's Vlissingen (Netherlands) warehouse from 2012 to mid-2017. Regressions (available on request) provide no evidence that this queue had any impact on aluminum premiums.

TABLE 5 Midwest aluminum premium estimates

		US balance measure		Both balance measures		
		Linear	Switching	Linear	Switching	
α	Intercept	0	149.9*** (19.7)	158.0*** (7.3)	151.2*** (20.2)	161.2*** (7.8)
		1		324.5*** (14.9)		287.7*** (18.0)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \alpha^1 = \alpha^0$			176.1*** [0.0000]		64.7*** [0.0000]
β_{US}	US market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0	158.4 (108.8)	74.2 (45.3)	147.0 (113.1)	46.5 (51.1)
		1		1300.2*** (212.2)		1502.0*** (673.3)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{US}^0$			33.4 [0.0000]		4.44** [0.0352]
β_{EU}	European market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0			-123.5 (226.6)	-282.0 (173.5)
		1				2149.7** (903.3)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{EU}^1 = \beta_{EU}^0$					5.39** [0.0202]
	Test $\chi^2(2) \beta_{US}^0 = \beta_{EU}^0$ and $\beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{EU}^1$					4.71* [0.0949]
γ_1	US share of world exchange stocks		-92.4 (68.5)	-95.9*** (28.4)	-100.4 (73.4)	-113.6*** (31.1)
γ_2	Detroit load-out queue		0.362*** (0.048)	0.220*** (0.017)	0.366*** (0.049)	0.223*** (0.016)
	Nonlinearity test: col. 2 $\chi^2(4)$, col. 4 $\chi^2(5)$			102.8*** [0.0000]		109.9*** [0.0000]
	RESET col. 1 $F_{2,184}$, col. 3 $F_{2,183}$		25.41*** [0.0000]		26.02*** [0.0000]	
	# Regime changes			11		2
	# Months in Regime 1			73		16
	R^2		0.728		0.729	
	sigma		45.87	32.78	45.90	32.10
	AIC		10.510	10.022	10.517	10.002
	BIC		10.579	10.176	10.602	10.190

Note: Sample September 2003–June 2019 (190 observations).

Columns 1 and 3, OLS, robust standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma denotes the equation standard error; columns 2 and 4, Maximum Likelihood, standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma estimated.

p-Values in [·] parentheses.

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; RESET, Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test.

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Intermediation costs may also have been influenced by the proximity of exchange warehouse stocks. I therefore include regional shares of LME warehouse stocks as a component of the x vector in Equations (1)–(3)—the US stock share, ss_{US} , in the equation for the MWP, the European stock share, ss_{EU} , in the equation for the Rotterdam Premium and the Asia share, ss_{AS} , in the Japanese Premium equation. Stocks and queue lengths (calendar days) are measured at the end of the month so I use a 1-month lag. (Definitions and sources for all the variables are provided in the appendix). The specific equation estimated, following specification (2), is therefore

$$prem_{jt} = \sum_{r=0}^1 p_{jt}^r \left[\alpha_j^r + \beta_j^r balance_{j,t-3} \right] + \gamma_{j1} ss_{j,t-1} + \gamma_{j2} qdt_{t-1} + u_{jt} \quad (j = US, EU, AS; t = 1, \dots, T). \quad (5)$$

The probabilities p_{jt}^r evolve according to Equation (3).

The basic estimation results for the three regional aluminum premiums are reported in columns 1 and 2 of Table 5 (MWP), Table 6 (Rotterdam Premium), and Table 7 (Japanese Premium). In each case, the premium is related to the regional market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months), the regional stock share and the Detroit load-out queue length. The first column of each table reports the OLS estimates of the linear model defined by Equation (5) subject to the restrictions of Equation (4). The second column reports the ML estimates of the switching model defined by Equations (3) and (5). The R^2 coefficient of determination is only available for the linear specification so model fit

TABLE 6 Rotterdam aluminum premium estimates

		US balance measure		Both balance measures		
		Linear	Switching	Linear	Switching	
α	Intercept	0	61.7*** (8.9)	61.7*** (4.9)	74.1*** (8.9)	61.4*** (3.5)
		1		118.1*** (7.0)		188.3*** (6.8)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \alpha^1 = \alpha^0$			185.2*** [0.0000]		415.3*** [0.0000]
β_{US}	US market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0			138.9*** (37.3)	120.9*** (15.2)
		1				999.4*** (69.3)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{US}^0$					154.6*** [0.0000]
β_{EU}	European market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0	16.6 (95.5)	21.3 (74.7)	9.8 (86.9)	165.8** (74.8)
		1		1521.7*** (218.0)		380.9*** (100.8)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{EU}^1 = \beta_{EU}^0$			8.94*** [0.0027]		3.38* [0.0662]
	Test $\chi^2(2) \beta_{US}^0 = \beta_{EU}^0$ and $\beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{EU}^1$					23.54*** [0.0000]
γ_1	European share of world exchange stocks		-4.4 (20.6)	-44.4*** (16.4)	-44.4 (86.9)	-15.6* (8.4)
γ_2	Detroit load-out queue		0.331*** (0.035)	0.320*** (0.018)	0.364 (0.037)	0.234*** (0.011)
Nonlinearity test: col. 2 $\chi^2(4)$, col. 4 $\chi^2(5)$				114.6*** [0.0000]		205.4*** [0.0000]
RESET col. 1 $F_{2,184}$, col. 3 $F_{2,183}$			16.13 [0.0000]		16.27 [0.0000]	
# Regime changes				11		4
# Months in Regime 1				73		51
R^2			0.822		0.845	
Sigma			33.62	21.50	31.49	16.53
AIC			9.889	9.338	9.763	8.745
BIC			9.957	9.492	9.848	8.933

Note: Sample September 2003–June 2019 (190 observations).

Columns 1 and 3, OLS, robust standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma denotes the equation standard error; columns 2 and 4, Maximum Likelihood, standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma estimated.

p-Values in [·] parentheses.

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; RESET, Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test.

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

should be judged by either the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) or the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) reported at the foot of the columns. In either case, a lower value indicates lower information loss, interpreted as a superior fit.

I first report two tests for departures from linearity (Hypothesis A). I test for departures from linearity. The tables report the Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test (RESET) specification test for the linear models (column 1). The null hypothesis of linearity is rejected in all three cases. Second the likelihood ratio test on the regime-switching specification (column 2) decisively rejects the linearity hypothesis.¹⁸ In all cases the AIC and BIC values fall sharply in moving from the linear to the regime-switching equation. I conclude that the data decisively reject the linear specification in favor of the Markov-switching model for all three premiums.

I turn now to Hypothesis B which asks whether premium spikes are associated with greater sensitivity to market conditions as measured by the *balance* variable. The second column of each table reports the β coefficients for the two

¹⁸The RESET tests for the significance of the square and cube of the fitted values from the reported regression on an augmented regression. The likelihood ratio test imposes equality on the α and β regime-switching coefficients and sets $\pi^{10} = \pi^{01} = 0$.

TABLE 7 Japanese aluminum premium estimates

		US balance measure		Both balance measures	
		Linear	Switching	Linear	Switching
α	Intercept	0	74.8 (11.5)	86.2*** (5.4)	83.4*** (12.4)
		1		210.4*** (15.2)	250.9*** (12.9)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \alpha^1 = \alpha^0$			88.8*** [0.0000]	198.9*** [0.0000]
β_{US}	US market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0			42.2 (36.7)
		1			-3.4 (19.4)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{US}^0$				1006.2*** (85.1)
β_{EU}	European market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0			488.6*** (94.8)
		1			312.7*** (109.1)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{EU}^1 = \beta_{EU}^0$				1363.2*** (159.0)
β_{AS}	Asian market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0	189.7 (140.2)	204.9*** (65.9)	
		1		871.3 (530.1)	
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{AS}^1 = \beta_{AS}^0$			1.41 [0.2356]	
γ_1	Asian share of world exchange stocks		8.7 (21.4)	-10.2 (12.0)	-9.4 (26.3)
γ_2	Detroit load-out queue		0.348*** (0.037)	0.250*** (0.013)	0.326*** (0.034)
	Nonlinearity test: col. 2 $\chi^2(4)$, col. 4 $\chi^2(5)$			101.7*** [0.0000]	130.0*** [0.0000]
	RESET col. 1 $F_{2,184}$, col. 3 $F_{2,183}$		19.09 [0.0000]		19.51 [0.0000]
	# Regime changes			2	2
	# Months in Regime 1			14	46
	R^2		0.832		0.848
	Sigma		33.54	24.09	31.93
	AIC		9.884	9.402	9.791
	BIC		9.953	9.556	9.876

Note: Sample September 2003–June 2019 (190 observations).

Columns 1 and 3, OLS, robust standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma denotes the equation standard error; columns 2 and 4, Maximum Likelihood, standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma estimated. *p*-Values in [·] parentheses.

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; RESET, Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test.

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

regimes. In all three cases we find $\beta^1 > \beta^0$. The likelihood ratio test rejects equality is rejected for the Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums but not the Japanese Premium (Table 7).¹⁹

Turning to the estimated γ coefficients, the expected negative relationship between the stock shares is evident from the column 2 ML estimates for the Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums but the stock coefficient in the Japanese equation is small and does not differ significantly from zero. The Detroit load-out queue is seen as having raised all three premiums by a similar amount and in each case the estimated coefficient is significantly greater than zero at the 1% level.

Both the US and Europe import seaborne aluminum from Russia. Transport costs from St. Petersburg to Baltimore and Rotterdam are similar with the consequence that supplies can be redirected at the margin to the more profitable

¹⁹The estimates of the β coefficients are imprecise in instances in which there are few observations in one of the two regimes. This qualification applies most strongly to the Midwest and Japanese premium estimates.

market. This suggests that the Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums may be sensitive to the market balance on both sides of the Atlantic. I examine this possibility in results reported in columns 3 and 4 of Tables 5 and 6. The AIC and BIC in column 4 of Table 6 both demonstrate that the extended specification is preferred for the Rotterdam Premiums and a likelihood ratio test rejects equality of the coefficients on the US and European market balance variables with the premium more sensitive to the US than to European conditions. The coefficient γ_1 of the European stock share loses significance in this extended specification while that of the Detroit load-out queue (γ_2) drops to close to the value in the MWP estimates.

The corresponding estimates in Table 5 for the MWP show the extended specification as performing better than the basic column 2 specification according to the AIC but not according to the more parsimonious BIC. The estimates reject the equality of the two sets of balance coefficients at the 10% level but not at the 5% level. I conclude that the basic specification in Equation (5), in which the premium is determined solely by US variables, provides a sufficient description of the behavior of the MWP.

This cross-Atlantic argument does not apply to Japan. Nevertheless, in view of the concern however that the Asian market balance may be poorly measured as the consequence of poorer market integration, I report estimates of a specification that relates the Japanese Premium to the US and European balance variables (Table 7 columns 3 and 4). The premium appears responsive to both balance variables with equality in the responses rejected at the 1% level. Both the AIC and BIC show that the modified specification to be preferred over the Equation (5) specification. In this specification, the Asian stock share variable exerts a negative influence that is statistically significant at the 5% level. The Detroit load-out queue acted to raise the Japanese premium but only to around half the extent of its impact on the Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums.

4.3 | Zinc premiums

Figure 4 charts the Midwest and Rotterdam zinc premiums together with the interest-adjusted LME backwardation. The following features are evident:

- No trend is apparent in either premium.
- There is a sharp peak in both the Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums in 2006–07 with Rotterdam Premium peaking a few months after the MWP. This peak coincided with an acute backwardation in the LME price.
- The MWP rose well above the Rotterdam Premium over the 5 years 2011–15 during a period in which the exchange market was in contango.

A substantial proportion of US zinc imports arrive through the port of New Orleans and, possibly for this reason, the LME's New Orleans warehouses have held the largest share of exchange warehouse stocks in the US. The share (*sno*) of global LME zinc stocks held in these warehouses rose from 40% at the end of 2003 to a peak of 99% at the end of 2017. This share subsequently fell back to around 45% in the first 6 months of 2019. A high concentration of stock in a particular location potentially allows the warehouse operators in that location to restrict access to inventory with a consequential impact on premiums. In addition, load-out queues developed from the New Orleans warehouses between 2010 and 2014. The New Orleans load-out queue (*qno*) was similar to the Detroit aluminum load-out queues albeit substantially shorter both in length and duration—see Figure 5.²⁰ Differently from the aluminum premium equations, the zinc premium equations also include the unlagged *balance* variable consistent with an immediate but regime-independent response of premiums to market conditions.

The basic equation estimated, following from specification (2), is therefore

$$prem_{jt} = \sum_{r=0}^1 p_{jt}^r \left[\alpha_j^r + \beta_j^r balance_{j,t-m_j} \right] + \gamma_{j1} sno_{t-1} + \gamma_{j2} qno_{t-1} + \gamma_{j3} balance_{jt} + u_t \quad (6)$$

($j = \text{US, EU}; t = 1, \dots, T$).

²⁰The queue length is as reported by the LME from April (2014). Before that date, the queue is calculated from the stock of canceled warrants using the procedure set out in Gilbert (2021b) for aluminum.

TABLE 8 Midwest zinc premium estimates

		US balance measure		Both balance measures		
		Linear	Switching	Linear	Switching	
α	Intercept	0	82.2*** (17.2)	98.1*** (5.9)	81.1*** (16.7)	87.6*** (6.4)
		1		147.6*** (8.3)		134.2*** (8.7)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \alpha^1 = \alpha^0$			143.3*** [0.0000]		140.1*** [0.0000]
β_{US}	US market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0	359.2*** (126.8)	144.3*** (45.3)	350.2*** (120.8)	168.5*** (45.7)
		1		591.0*** (46.4)		531.6*** (46.9)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{US}^0$			78.9*** [0.0000]		51.6*** [0.0000]
β_{EU}	European market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0			134.0 (100.7)	-73.7 (48.4)
		1				240.7*** (64.1)
	Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{EU}^1 = \beta_{EU}^0$					16.5*** [0.0000]
	Test $\chi^2(2) \beta_{US}^0 = \beta_{EU}^0$ and $\beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{EU}^1$					25.46*** [0.0000]
γ_1	New Orleans stock share		88.0*** (23.2)	13.41 (11.15)	90.66*** (22.49)	34.24*** (11.70)
γ_2	New Orleans load-out queue		0.262*** (0.043)	0.196*** (0.028)	0.237*** (0.045)	0.160*** (0.029)
γ_3	Current regional market balance		179.8* (100.4)	137.0*** (40.1)	156.8 (95.6)	103.9** (44.4)
Nonlinearity test: col. 2 $\chi^2(4)$, col. 4 $\chi^2(5)$				130.4*** [0.0000]		141.5*** [0.0000]
RESET col. 1 $F_{2,184}$, col. 3 $F_{2,183}$			48.48 [0.0000]		48.46 [0.0000]	
# Regime changes				5		5
# Months in Regime 1				75		77
R^2			0.658		0.669	
Sigma			29.80	19.15	29.43	18.23
AIC			9.653	9.019	9.633	8.951
BIC			9.738	9.190	9.735	9.157

Note: Sample September 2003–June 2019 (190 observations).

Columns 1 and 3, OLS, robust standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma denotes the equation standard error; columns 2 and 4, Maximum Likelihood, standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma estimated.

p-Values in [·] parentheses.

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; RESET, Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test.

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

The balance variable is again a 3-month average lagged by 3 months in the MWP estimates (hence $m_{US} = 3$), but lagged by 6 months ($m_{EU} = 6$) in the Rotterdam Premium estimates. The probabilities p_{jt}^r evolve according to Equation (3).

Equation estimates are reported in Table 8 (MWP) and Table 9 (Rotterdam Premium) which have the same structure as Tables 5 and 6. The first two columns of each table report OLS estimates of the linear version of Equation (6), that is, with the restrictions given by Equation (4), and the second column reports ML estimates of the regime-switching specification.

I first consider linearity (Hypothesis A). The RESET tests reported at the foot of column 1 of the two tables both reject linearity. The same is true of the likelihood ratio tests at the foot of column 2 of the two tables. In both cases the AIC and BIC values in column 2 are lower than those in column 1. As was the case with aluminum, the data decisively reject the linear specification in favor of the Markov-switching model. Turning to Hypothesis B, the second column of each table reports the β coefficients for the two regimes. In both cases we find $\beta^1 > \beta^0$ with the likelihood ratio test rejecting equality.

The estimated γ coefficients show that the New Orleans share of world stocks raised the MWP but there is no evidence of a corresponding impact on the Rotterdam Premium. Similarly, the New Orleans load-out queue had a

TABLE 9 Rotterdam zinc premium estimates

	US balance measure		Both balance measures	
	Linear	Switching	Linear	Switching
α				
Intercept	0	137.2*** (18.4)	152.8*** (19.1)	108.7*** (3.7)
	1	154.9*** (8.7)		194.6*** (6.7)
Equality test $\chi^2(1) \alpha^1 = \alpha^0$		16.5*** [0.0000]		204.8*** [0.0000]
β_{US}				
US market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0		415.7*** (128.3)	55.9** (19.8)
	1			945.9*** (37.8)
Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{US}^0$				434.8*** [0.0000]
β_{EU}				
European market balance (3-month average, lagged 3 months)	0	447.5** (179.1)	286.4*** (97.7)	-47.7* (28.4)
	1		2322.4*** (151.0)	-127.6 (122.4)
Equality test $\chi^2(1) \beta_{EU}^1 = \beta_{EU}^0$			246.6*** [0.0000]	0.40 [0.4291]
Test $\chi^2(2) \beta_{US}^0 = \beta_{EU}^0$ and $\beta_{US}^1 = \beta_{EU}^1$				56.65*** [0.0000]
γ_1		7.18 (25.9)	-20.2 (26.9)	9.16* (5.29)
γ_2		-0.255*** (0.084)	-0.170*** (0.047)	0.049*** (0.019)
γ_3		687.2*** (179.1)	670.5*** (130.9)	84.5*** (32.0)
Nonlinearity test: col. 2 $\chi^2(4)$, col. 4 $\chi^2(5)$				355.6*** [0.0000]
RESET col. 1 $F_{2,184}$, col. 3 $F_{2,183}$		102.9 [0.0000]	214.5 [0.0000]	
# Regime changes		2		2
# Months in Regime 1		23		32
R^2		0.462	0.637	
Sigma		41.93	20.05	12.63
AIC		10.336	9.027	8.144
BIC		10.421	9.197	8.349
			10.055	8.316

Note: Sample September 2003–June 2019 (190 observations).

Columns 1 and 3, OLS, robust standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma denotes the equation standard error; columns 2 and 4, Maximum Likelihood, standard errors in (·) parentheses, sigma estimated. p -Values in [·] parentheses.

Abbreviations: AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; RESET, Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test.

***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

positive impact on the MWP, similar in size to the impact of the Detroit aluminum load-out queue on the aluminum premium, but there is no evidence of an impact on the Rotterdam Premium.

Columns 3 and 4 of Tables 8 and 9 condition on both the US and European market balances. This gives a dramatic improvement in fit for the MWP equation (compare columns 1 and 3). There is a modest improvement in fit for the MWP estimates (Table 8) but the substantive conclusions, including those relating to the New Orleans stock share and load-out queue, are unaltered. The corresponding results for the Rotterdam Premium (Table 9) give rise to negative β estimates for the European deficit. The BIC indicates that a superior fit is obtained by setting the two β_{EU} coefficients to zero (compare columns 4 and 5). This final set of estimates implies that although the Rotterdam zinc premium is influenced by the European market balance, the spike in 2006–07 was driven by US market factors. Differently from the column 2 estimates, the estimates in columns 4 and 5 show a positive impact from the New Orleans stock share and (at the 10% level in column 5) from the New Orleans load-out queue.

4.4 | Observations

The results for both aluminum and zinc provide strong confirmation for the claim that there are two regimes in premium determination. Premiums respond strongly to demand conditions in periods of tight demand but are principally determined by the costs of intermediating exchange warehouses in the latter periods which are more extended. The estimates for each of the Midwest and Rotterdam aluminum and zinc premiums reject the linear specification (Hypothesis A) and demonstrate that premium spikes are driven by heightened sensitivity to the US and European market balances (Hypothesis B).

In periods of balanced demand, premiums are determined by the costs of intermediating exchange warehouse stocks. In terms of the estimates in Tables 5–9, these costs are reflected in the stock share variables in the aluminum premium equations and in the impact of the Detroit and New Orleans load-out variables. The higher the share of total aluminum exchange stocks in the region in question, the lower the regional premium, other things being equal. (This effect is not visible in the zinc market where high levels of stock were held in the LME's New Orleans exchange warehouses). Warehouse load-out queues raise the costs of taking metal from exchange warehouses by imposing additional interest and warehouse rental costs that can be avoided by direct purchase from a smelter or merchant. The Detroit aluminum load-out queue raised the respective Midwest and Rotterdam Premiums by comparable amounts and suggest a smaller impact on the Japanese Premium. In zinc, the New Orleans load-out queue had a similar impact on the Midwest zinc premium but it is less clear whether there was also an impact on the Rotterdam zinc premium.

Table 10 summarizes the months attributed to Regime 1 in which the premiums are very sensitive to the market balance. These attributions are based on the smoothed probabilities from the best-fitting estimates in Tables 5–9, as judged by the BIC (Table 5, column 2; Tables 6–8, column 4; Table 9, column 5). Table 11 summarizes the average

TABLE 10 High response periods

		2005–08	2009–16	2017–19
Aluminum	Midwest			Jan. 2014
	(T5, C2)			Apr. 2015
	Rotterdam		Apr. 2010	Feb. 2014
	(T6, C4)		Apr. 2013	Mar. 2015
	Japan		Jul. 2011	
	(T7, C4)		Apr. 2015	
Zinc	Midwest	Aug. 2005	Feb. 2011	Mar. 2017
	(T8, C4)	Jun. 2007	Mar. 2016	Jun. 2019
	Rotterdam	Sep. 2005		
	(T9, C5)	Apr. 2008		

Note: The table reports start dates and end dates of periods of tight demand, identified as those periods where the smoothed probability of being in Regime 1 exceeds 0.5. Table references: (Tx, Cy) reads “calculated from the estimates reported in Table x, column y.”

TABLE 11 Regime characteristics

	Regime	Aluminum			Zinc	
		Midwest	Rotterdam	Japan	Midwest	Rotterdam
Average premium (\$/ton)	0	155.69	72.12	88.40	100.88	115.51
	1	417.72	195.25	241.01	174.46	239.08
Monthly change (%)	0	0.92	0.57	0.20	-0.36	0.12
	1	3.54	2.31	1.96	1.02	1.07

deflated premiums and the average monthly percentage change for the two regimes as identified in Table 10. In each case, premiums are higher and more variable in the high response periods. The high response periods into three groups:

- 2005–08: This was the start of the so-called “commodities super-cycle” period in which rapid Chinese economic growth led to tightness across the entire ferrous and nonferrous metals industries with aluminum, where China was a net-exporter, being the sole exception (Radetzki, 2006, Chap. 6; Radetzki & Wårell, 2017). The zinc market was particularly tight as evidenced by the backwardation—see Figure 4. Tight demand emerged first in the United States and then generalized to Europe.²¹
- 2009–16: The super-cycle was interrupted by the 2008–09 Global Financial Crisis but nonferrous markets tightened again from 2010 stimulated initially by Chinese stockpiling. This resulted in a gradual recovery of both prices and premiums. The US aluminum market remained well-supplied through to the end of 2013 when it jumped up to an unprecedented level.
- 2017–19: Zinc provided the exception to relatively depressed nonferrous metals prices over this post-super-cycle period. Gilbert (2021a) attributes the tightness of the zinc market to the October 2015 decision by a dominant producer to substantially reduce production at one of its major mines.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Most commodity futures market contracts are written in terms of a geographically restricted range of delivery locations. So-called cash prices relate to these specifications and locations and, in many cases, will these will be taken as the front futures price. Transactions prices for lots of the standard specification in locations close to the futures market delivery points will be equal to or very close to the front futures price. Cash prices in other locations will differ from front futures prices creating basis risk. This will apply in particular to commercial transactions outside the United States for commodities traded on US exchanges.

Contracts on the LME, currently the dominant world futures market for nonferrous metals, differ from this standard model in ways which allow it to generate an unambiguous global cash price on each trading day. This gives a misleading impression that LME cash prices can be taken as representing transaction prices in commercial sales throughout the world. In fact, transactions prices differ from LME cash prices by regional premiums. These have been low and stable in copper but at various times in the other nonferrous markets they have been affected by market tightness and inefficiencies in the market for exchange warehouse services. Transactions prices are easily available from price reporting agencies for the most important regions and provide a more reliable guide to the prices paid by consumers and received by producers.

LME cash prices define the price of LME warrants that entitle the holder to take delivery of the metal and not the price of the metal itself. The LME maintains warehouses throughout the United States, Western Europe, and Asia. Due to seller optionality, the metal denominated by a specific warrant may well be in a location that is geographically inconvenient for

²¹US trade data show unwrought zinc imports from Europe to a total value of \$131.8m over the 6 months October 2006 to March 2007. By comparison, imports totaled only \$0.1m in the 12 months October 2005–September 2006. Source: US Department of Commerce, USA Trade Online, <https://usatrade.census.gov/data/Perspective60/Dim/dimension.aspx>. The 2006–07 period of tight zinc market conditions coincides with the period (November 2005–January 2007) over which Figuerola-Ferretti et al. (2015) found that the LME zinc price manifested weakly explosive behavior. The estimates in this paper support their view that the rapid rise in zinc prices over that period was due to physical market conditions rather than being a rational bubble.

the intending purchaser and possibly of an inappropriate product specification. The purchaser will need to use the broker warrant market to swap the delivered warrant for an alternative to take delivery of metal in a convenient location. This will add to purchase costs. The consequence is that consumers will almost invariably prefer to purchase directly from a producer or from the merchant market. The option of exchange purchase puts a floor on the price the consumers will pay but they will generally pay significantly more to avoid the costs and inconvenience of exchange purchase. In particular, premiums tend to be higher in a region in which accounts for a relatively low proportion of world stocks.

Intermediation costs, and hence premiums, reflect competition in the market for exchange warehouse services. The zinc market has seen the concentration of exchange stocks in a small number of locations, with a single location (New Orleans) accounting for almost the entirety of these stocks in the US for much of the period under examination. This lack of competition has the potential to raise exchange intermediation costs, and the evidence shows that this impact has been significant. A second inefficiency, warehouse load-out queues, has had an even larger impact on aluminum and, to a lesser extent, zinc premiums. Queues raise intermediation costs because the buyer incurs additional interest and warehousing costs before being able to take delivery. In aluminum, at their peak load-out queues reached over 2 years.

In a well-supplied market and absent monopoly power in the exchange warehouse services market, competition will force premiums down to be close to the floor determined by the costs of intermediating exchange warehouses. However, if market conditions are tight and metal consumers become urgent to obtain additional supplies, premiums can rise dramatically. This leads to a sharp peak in premiums as observed in the zinc market in 2006–07 and the aluminum market in 2014. Although generally low, the resulting regional premiums can rise to over 20% of the full price in terms of tight demand. Premium dynamics share features with futures backwardations, but the two are caused by common factors rather than either causing the other.

Price behavior of this sort can be characterized by a Markov-switching regime change model. This paper has employed models which randomly shift from a normal situation, in which premiums reflect the costs of intermediating exchange warehouses and where demand conditions have a relatively small influence, to a less frequent tight demand regime in which premiums are much more sensitive to demand conditions. Models of this class substantially outperform standard linear models in terms of fit. Standard linear models can result in biased coefficient estimates through incorrect attribution of demand effects to other modeled factors. Estimates for aluminum and zinc show that such periods tend to originate in the US and then to generalize to other regions, probably as the consequence of diversion of metal to higher premium markets.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data used in this study are available from <https://sites.google.com/site/christopherlesliegilbert/data>.

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DATA CITATION

Metals premium data; not publicly available; data can be obtained from S&P Platts on payment of a data license fee.
LME and NYMEX price data; not publicly available; data can be obtained from *Metal Bulletin*—Fastmarkets on payment of a data license fee.

LME warehouse stock data; not publicly available; data can be obtained from the LME on payment of a data license fee.
LME warehouse load-out queue data: LME, <https://www.lme.com/en-GB/Market-Data/Reports-and-data/Warehouse-and-stocks-reports/Warehouse-and-queue-data>.

Aluminum and zinc production and consumption data, data can be obtained from the CRU Group Ltd. on payment of a data license fee.

US Producer Price Index (all items). IMF, *International Financial Statistics*, <https://data.imf.org>.

Interest rate: Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/RIFSPFAAD90NB>.

DATA APPENDIX

Premium data are from S&P Platts. Data codes and descriptions are taken from the data source. *US Midwest Premiums*

Aluminum	MMAKE03	Aluminum P1020 Transaction Premium delivered US Midwest Mavg, c/lb converted to \$/mt
	MMOJU03	Aluminum P1020 Transaction Price (Implied Duty-Unpaid) Delivered US Midwest \$/mt Mavg (quoted starting August 2018; March-July 2018 author's extrapolation)
Copper	MMACP03	Copper Cathode Premium delivered US Midwest MAvg, c/lb converted to \$/mt
Lead	MMXCD03	Lead Premium delivered US Midwest Mavg, c/lb converted to \$/mt
Nickel	MMAZMO4	Nickel Cathode Prem Spot US, averaged over month, c/lb converted to \$/mt
Zinc	MMAZH00	Zinc MW SHG Premium averaged over month, c/lb converted to \$/mt

Rotterdam Premiums

Aluminum	AALVK00	Aluminum Good Western Premium Duty-Unpaid in-warehouse Rotterdam Mavg, \$/mt
Copper	MMAYR04	Copper (Grd A) Prem Rotterdam, averaged monthly, \$/mt
Lead	MMAYV04	Lead 99.985% Prem Rotterdam monthly, \$/mt
Nickel	AALWK00	Nickel Briq Prem IW Rdam MAvg, \$/mt
Zinc	MMAYN04	Zinc (SHG) Prem Rotterdam monthly, \$/mt

Asian premiums

Aluminum	AAMDP00	Aluminum Prem, CIF Japan Mavg, \$/mt
Copper	MMAMK00	Copper Prem, C&F China, \$/mt
Zinc	MMANE00	Zinc Prem In Warehouse Singapore, \$/mt

Exchange prices

Aluminum, copper (except US), lead, nickel, and zinc: Daily LME Settlement prices, \$/mt, averaged over the month, downloaded from *Fastmarkets-Metal Bulletin*.

US copper: NYMEX (COMEX) closing price, front contract, c/lb converted to \$/mt, averaged over the month, downloaded from *Fastmarkets-Metal Bulletin*.

Contango

The contango is measured as the (dollar) difference between the LME 3-month and Settlement Prices, adjusted by the 90-day AA Financial Commercial Paper Interest Rate and deflated by the US PPI. Source for interest rate data (RIFSPFAAD90NB); Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/RIFSPFAAD90NB>. The backwardation is the negative of the contango.

Full prices

Calculated as the sum of the monthly LME price plus the regional premium, except for US copper, where the MWTP is the sum of the monthly NYMEX (COMEX) price plus the MWP.

Deflation

All premiums and prices are deflated by the US Producer Price Index (all items). *Source:* IMF, International Financial Statistics. <https://data.imf.org>.

Variables used in regressions

LME warehouse stocks: Final day of month. *Source:* *LME Warehouse Stock Movements:* <https://www.lme.com/Market-Data/Accessing-market-data/Historical-data>.

LME warehouse load-out queue lengths (Detroit and New Orleans): *LME Warehouse Stocks and Queue Reports* (from April 2014).

<https://www.lme.com/en-GB/Market-Data/Reports-and-data/Warehouse-and-stocks-reports/Warehouse-and-queue-data>.

Before April 2014: Author's estimates from the end month stock of canceled warrants in conjunction with prevailing LME warehouse rules. *Source* for canceled warrant data: *LME Warehouse Stock Movements:* <https://www.lme.com/Market-Data/Accessing-market-data/Historical-data>.

US and European aluminum and zinc market balance measures: Calculated from quarterly US and European aluminum and zinc consumption, aluminum smelter production, and zinc slab production data interpolated into a monthly basis. *Source:* <https://www.crugroup.com/>. The resulting balance series are detrended and deseasonalized using STAMP (Koopman et al., 2009).